

EFFECT OF DIFFERENT TILLAGE PRACTICES AND IRRIGATION REGIMES ON GROWTH AND YIELD OF WHEAT CROP

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Abstract

Wheat is an important cereal crop globally, providing dietary energy and protein. It is crucial to optimize agricultural practices to increase crop yield and sustainability. Traditional ploughing techniques may cause soil erosion, organic matter loss, and decreased soil fertility. Conventional tillage (CT), minimum tillage (MT), and zero tillage (ZT), techniques have drawn interest as sustainable substitutes. Therefore, a field experiment was carried out to study the impact of three tillage practices CT (two passes of disk plow and rotavator followed by a leveler), MT (two passes of rotavator followed by a leveler), and ZT (no-tillage) practices combined with four irrigation regimes (0, 2, 4, and 6 irrigations) on crop development and yield of wheat crop during the rabi season 2021-2022 in Shaheed Benazirabad. The experiment was design as split-plot design; three tillage practices CT, MT, and ZT practices were kept as main plot and four irrigation regimes were arranged randomly in the sub-plots. Each treatment was a combination of tillage and irrigation treatment. Results illustrated that the CT compared with MT and ZT practices has substantially ($P < 0.05$) improved the crop growth (i.e., tillers and plant height), yield attributes (i.e., effective and non-effective tillers per square meter, filled and unfilled spikelet's per panicle, spike length, grains per spike, and 1000 grains weight), grain yield, and biomass. Moreover, results presented that the tillage practices and irrigation had substantial effect on effective and non-effective tillers, filled and unfilled spikelet's per panicle, spike length, grain numbers per spike, 1000 grains weight, biomass, grain yield, and crop water productivity. CT compared with MT and ZT practice has substantially ($P < 0.05$) higher grain yield (8.93% and 12.08%), biomass (11.10% and 27.58%), and crop water productivity (47.02%, and 90.77%) at all irrigation levels. In terms of irrigation regimes, six times irrigation, compared

with 0, 2, and 4 irrigations significantly higher grain yield (205.51%, 84.43%, and 27.76%, respectively) and biomass (163.84%, 40.37, and 16.40%, respectively). Based on the results, the CT combined with 6 irrigations produced higher crop growth, yield attributes, grain yield, and biomass. These findings contributed to the understanding of the interactions between tillage practices and irrigation regimes on crop growth, yield, biomass, and WP of wheat crop. Moreover, provided valuable knowledge for farmers, agronomists, and policymakers in their decision-making processes.

INTRODUCTION

Around the world, wheat is a staple grain that is widely utilized. Wheat is consumed in Pakistan in significantly greater quantities than other staples (Shaheen et al., 2020). Providing 1.6% of GDP overall and 8.9% of agricultural value added, wheat is essential to the nation's economy (GoP, 2019). About 26.67 million tons of grain were harvested from 8.97 million hectares of wheat in the planting year 2016–17, with an average yield of 2973 kg/ha. In Sindh, it was farmed on 1.17 million hectares, 3.91 million tons of grain were produced, and the average yield was 3342 kg/ha. Given that Sindh's average wheat yield is 11% greater than Pakistan's, the province has a lot of potential for wheat production (PSY, 2019).

In many areas, the availability of water is a major issue restricting agricultural output. When crops are properly irrigated, they receive the optimum amount of water at the right time, promoting the best possible growth and development. Improper techniques, such as excessive or insufficient irrigation, can have a detrimental effect on soil health, water usage efficiency, and wheat output. Efficiency and individual factor output are significantly impacted by water shortage, particularly in semi-arid environments. Due to increased non-beneficial evapotranspiration, surface irrigation techniques may only be 30–40% effective for Rabi crops (Rajanna et al., 2016).

Over 40% of wheat produced in developing nations is produced using irrigated systems (Rajaram et al., 2007). The amount and growth of wheat are significantly influenced by the frequency of watering. Grain yields may increase with increased watering frequency (Han et al., 2020). It has been noted that deficit irrigation affects wheat's water-use efficiency (WUE) as well as yield (Galavi et al., 2012). Since skipping irrigation during important development

stages can dramatically lower grain output, efficient irrigation scheduling is essential for water management (Kumar et al., 2014).

Additionally, research has looked into how different irrigation schedules affect the productivity of wheat crops. The impacts of deficit irrigation on wheat output and water usage efficiency were studied by Wang et al. in 2021. According to their findings, controlled deficit irrigation techniques might raise water productivity without appreciably lowering wheat production, striking a long-term equilibrium between crop productivity and water conservation.

Ploughing, harrowing, and cultivating are examples of tillage techniques that alter the structure of the soil, the availability of nutrients, water retention, and weed control. These factors then influence the development and production of wheat crops. Ploughing and other conventional techniques have the potential to degrade soil, increase erosion, and decrease water penetration. Alternative tillage techniques, such as conservation tillage (also known as reduced tillage or zero tillage), are becoming more and more well-liked because they enhance water conservation, improve soil health, and decrease erosion. Studies have indicated that as compared to conventional tillage, no-tillage and low tillage methods enhance soil structure, lessen erosion, and boost wheat output.

The stability of the soil used to produce crops is greatly impacted by tillage techniques. The structure, aggregate stability, infiltration ability, water-holding capacity, loosening of hard ground, and other properties of the soil are all improved by proper tillage. However, inappropriate tillage can result in the breakdown of soil aggregation and structure, which can impact the soil's ability to hold water and allow for infiltration. This can wash away important nutrients, cause soil erosion, and have other negative

effects on the soil and plants that are planted (Hammel, 1989; Keshavarzpour, 2013).

The amount of nitrogen in soil that is available to plants depends on how quickly carbon is mineralized. Because crop residues on the soil surface more effectively immobilize nitrogen, no-till farming practices have frequently been linked to decreased nitrogen bioavailability (Wang et al., 2008). But it's interesting to note that, in contrast to conventional tillage techniques, nitrogen increase has been noted under the no-tillage strategy (Jat et al., 2018). Compared to approaches that entail integrating straw into the soil, the application of crop wastes assists in nutrient cycling and the intensity of mineralization, resulting in decreased nitrogen accessible under no-till systems. On the other side, conventional tillage approaches increase soil temperature, which promotes mineralization and speeds up the breakdown of organic matter (Rani et al., 2019).

Tillage techniques and irrigation timing are critical for maximizing soil water conservation and optimizing wheat grain output. Wheat is a very important cereal crop. To save energy, tillage might be eliminated or minimized. It is necessary to decrease irrigation or increase the wheat crop's efficiency in using soil water (Mrabet, 2000). No-tillage farming produced grain yields that were

equivalent to those of traditional tillage farming while using less water (Weber et al., 2000).

The physical, chemical, and biological properties of the soil are impacted by tillage. While inappropriate tillage can damage soil structure, speed erosion, decrease soil organic matter, and interfere with nutrient activities, correct tillage techniques can aid in addressing soil-related restrictions. To sustain soil functioning, promote nutrient cycling, and increase soil resilience, soil organic matter must be preserved and enhanced (Fornara et al., 2009; Madejón et al., 2007; Singh et al., 2009).

Maximum wheat production may be achieved with appropriate irrigation and tillage techniques. On the other hand, overwatering crops raises their production costs, and overtilling can pollute the environment (Alam et al., 2008; Pezzuolo et al., 2017). This study attempts to quantify the impact of conventional tillage, minimum tillage, and zero tillage with various irrigation regimes on the growth and production of wheat crop in light of the aforementioned facts and figures.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

An experiment was conducted at village Haji Khan Mari, Shaheed Benazirabad during Rabi season of 2021-22. The experimental area lies at 26.2988 °N latitude and 68.2385°E longitude at an elevation of about 31 m above sea level.

Figure. 1: Map of study area

Experimental design and layout

The study evaluated the impact of various irrigation schedules and tillage techniques on the production and growth of the wheat crop. Split-plot design concepts served as the foundation for the experiment's execution. In the major blocks, tillage procedures were established, and in the sub-blocks, various irrigation treatments were placed at random (Figure 3.2). Three tillage practices were used in the treatments: zero tillage (ZT), minimal tillage (MT), and conventional tillage (CT). For CT, two passes of the disc plough and rotavator were followed by a leveller; for MT, two rotavator passes were followed by a leveller; and for ZT, no tillage was used. No irrigation, two irrigations [at days 21 and 85 after sowing (DAS)], four irrigations [at days 21, 45, 65, 85, 105, and 120 DAS], and six irrigations [at days 21, 45, 65, 85, 105, and 120 DAS] were the irrigation schedules maintained. Tillage and irrigation

treatments were combined to create each treatment. Twelve treatments in all were used in the investigation. A further three replications of each treatment were conducted. The experimental plot was 20 by 28 metres in total (560 m²). Three primary blocks, each measuring 6 by 8 metres, were created from the entire area. The primary plots were separated by a 2.25 m buffer, and the unit plot was 1.5 m by 5 m. At least one week prior to seeding, these plots were prepared using various tillage techniques. The following was the label for the treatments:

- CT0, CT2, CT4, CT6 = Conventional tillage with 0, 2, 4, and 6 irrigations, respectively.
- MT0, MT2, MT4, MT6 = Minimum tillage with 0, 2, 4, and 6 irrigations, respectively.
- ZT0, ZT2, ZT4, ZT6 = Zero tillage with 0, 2, 4, and 6 irrigations, respectively.

Figure 2: Layout of the experimental field

Crop management

During the second week of December, 100 kg ha⁻¹ of wheat (TD-1) was drilled by hand. The wheat crop received 120:90:60 kg/ha of chemical fertilizers, such as NPK (Phullan et al., 2017). When preparing the field for seed sowing, the whole amount of P and K and half of the N were administered once as a baseline dosage. Equal amounts of the leftover N were sprayed during the first and second irrigations. Every plot had the same agronomic treatments, with the exception of the manual weed management.

Irrigation

Volumetric control was utilized for irrigation application. With the border irrigation method, pre-planting irrigation was 100 mm, and post-planting irrigation was 75 mm each.

Crop growth measurement-Plant height

As plant growth is affected by both genetic composition and the environment, the height of the plant serves as an indicator of dwarfing. Using a ruler, the distance from the ground to the tip of the leaf or the average top of the terminal spikelet

(excluding awns) was measured. If a plant was leaning before measurement, it was gently pushed into a vertical position.

Tillers

When tillers emerge from the leaf ligules, they are often counted. The number of tillers per meter row was counted every two weeks from the chosen length of one meter, from the first irrigation until harvest. Three replications, each one meter in length, were sampled for each treatment.

Harvesting

In order to investigate grain yield, straw yield, effective tillers, kernel weight, and other characteristics, crops were physically harvested as they reached maturity and gathered. A set length of a 1 m crop row was manually picked before the irrigation treatment began, and it was properly wrapped in paper to protect the plants and grains. Using ten randomly chosen plants from this one-meter sample, the post-harvest characteristics, such as panicle length, number of spikes per panicle, number of grains per spike, etc., were examined. On

the other hand, before the samples were threshed, the number of full and unfilled ear-heads, or panicles, from a 1 m² crop sample was counted to identify the effective and ineffective tillers. The harvested crop was manually threshed and winnowed, and the clean grain was then sun dried until the moisture content reached 10% (Gao et al., 2014).

Soil sampling

In each plot, the core sampler randomly took soil samples for examination at depths of 0-20, 20-40, and 40-60 cm. Prior to the seeding of a wheat crop, the physical characteristics of the soil, such as its texture, bulk density, and soil aggregation, as well as its chemical characteristics, such as pH, electrical conductivity (EC), soil nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), potassium (K), and soil organic carbon (SOC), were assessed. The soil samples were examined in Sakrand, Shaheed Benazirabad, at the soil and water testing facility. The following protocols were used to analyze each parameter:

Physical properties

Soil texture

Soil texture was determined using Bouyoucos Hydrometer method (Bouyoucos, 1927).

Dry bulk density

The dry bulk density was determined by gravimetric method (Blake et al., 1986) using following relation:

$$\text{Dry bulk density } (\rho_d) = \frac{\text{Dry weight of soil}}{\text{Total volume of soil}}$$

Chemical properties

A digital pH and EC meter was used to measure the pH and EC of soil samples. The available soil N

content was determined using the Kjeldahl technique. An ultraviolet visible spectrophotometer with absorbance below 700 nm wavelengths were used to quantify the amount of accessible soil P, while using flame photometry to determine the soil's K level. The technique of Walkley et al. (1934) was used to calculate the organic carbon content of the soil. According to Mattingly et al. (1974), soil organic matter was calculated by multiplying the organic carbon by a factor of 1.72.

Water productivity (WP)

Water productivity (WP) was calculated using the following formula (Tagar et al., 2016):

$$\text{Water productivity (kg m}^{-3}\text{)} = \frac{\text{Crop yield (kg ha}^{-1}\text{)}}{\text{Total water consumed (m}^3\text{ ha}^{-1}\text{)}}$$

Statistical analysis

A split-plot model was used to analyze all parameters. Tillage practices and irrigation means was separated using the Duncan's multiple range test at P < 0.05. The SPSS 24.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, III, USA) statistical software was used for analysis of variance (ANOVA).

RESULTS

Physical properties of soil

Table 4.1 provides information about the particle size distribution, texture class, and dry density for each depth range of experimental site. The soil texture class was silty clay loam for 0-60 cm soil profile. Additionally, the dry density of the soil slightly varies from 1.32-1.35 g/cm³ from 0-60 cm depth. The mean bulk density was measured 1.33 g/cm³ for 0-60 cm soil depth.

Table 1 Physical properties of soil under different soil depth

Depth (cm)	Particle size distribution (%)			Texture class	Dry density (g/cm ³)
	Sand	Silt	Clay		
0-20	25.4	44.5	30.1	Silty clay loam	1.32
21-40	25.1	45.3	29.6	Silty clay loam	1.33
41-60	24.7	46.8	28.5	Silty clay loam	1.35
Mean	25.06	45.53	29.4	Silty clay loam	1.33

Soil chemical properties

The average soil EC, pH, and SOM in 0-60 cm layer was 0.95 dS m⁻¹, 7.98, and 0.24% respectively (Table

4.2). The available soil N, P, and K was 0.05%, 2.51 mg kg⁻¹, and 284 mg kg⁻¹ for 0-60 cm soil layer, respectively.

Table 2 Soil chemical properties under different soil depth

Depth (cm)	EC (dS/m)	pH	SOC (%)	N (%)	P (mg kg ⁻¹)	K (mg kg ⁻¹)
0-20	0.93	8.1	0.24	0.047	2.40	282
21-40	0.95	7.96	0.24	0.045	2.54	284
41-60	0.98	7.89	0.24	0.044	2.58	286
Mean	0.95	7.98	0.24	0.05	2.51	284

Irrigation

Table 3 shows the irrigation date, total irrigation amount applied, water for seedlings, rainfall, and total depth of water applied under all treatments. The first irrigation was applied at 21 DAS for all

treatments. Before sowing 100 mm of basal dose was applied in all treatments. There was no rainfall recorded during the whole wheat growing season. Total water applied at 2, 4, and 6 irrigations was 250, 400, and 550 mm, respectively.

Table 3 Irrigation dates and total water applied under all treatments.

Treatments	Date (DAS)	Total irrigation amount (mm)	Water for seedling (mm)	Rainfall (mm)	Total water applied (mm)
CT0	-	0	100	0	100
MT0	-	0	100	0	100
ZT0	-	0	100	0	100
CT2	21, 85	150	100	0	250
MT2	21, 85	150	100	0	250
ZT2	21, 85	150	100	0	250
CT4	21, 45, 65, 105	300	100	0	400
MT4	21, 45, 65, 105	300	100	0	400
ZT4	21, 45, 65, 105	300	100	0	400
CT6	21, 45, 65, 85, 105, 120	450	100	0	550
MT6	21, 45, 65, 85, 105, 120	450	100	0	550
ZT6	21, 45, 65, 85, 105, 120	450	100	0	550

Growth parameters-Plant height

The plant height was measured fortnightly during crop growth presents in Figure 3. The plant height grew faster at 6 irrigations followed by 4, 2, and no irrigations. CT practices had substantially higher crop plant height compared with MT and ZT practices at all irrigations treatments. The maximum plant height was achieved under CT6 (74.0 ± 0.58 cm) followed by MT6 (70.67 ± 0.88 cm) and ZT6 (54

± 0.58 cm) on DAS 98. Maximum plant height was measured lowest under ZT0 (42.67 ± 0.88 cm) followed by MT0 (48.00 ± 0.58), and CT0 (53.33 ± 0.88 cm) practices on DAS 98. At all tillage practices 6 irrigations had significantly higher maximum plant height compared with 4, 2, and 0 irrigations. Maximum plant height was significantly influenced by tillage practices, irrigations, and tillage practices × irrigations.

Figure 3: Plant height under different treatments. Vertical bars indicate mean ± standard error

Tillers

The fortnight measured number of tillers per meter of row length presented in Figure 4. Tillers increased rapidly under CT practices compared with MT and ZT practices at 6, 4, 2, and 0 irrigation. The number of tillers was reduced as the irrigation reduced from 6 to no irrigation under all tillage practices. It was measured that CT practices compared with MT and ZT practices yielded higher number of tillers at 6, 4, 2, and 0 irrigation. The tillers increased gradually up to DAS 84 then started to decline. The maximum

number of tillers was measured under CT6 (403.67 ± 4.26) followed by MT6 (384.33 ± 4.16) and ZT6 (376.33 ± 9.02) on DAS 84. Results illustrated those increasing irrigations number of tillers also improved. At no irrigation number of tillers decreased substantially under all tillage practices. Statistical analysis indicated that tillage practices and irrigations significantly affect maximum number of tillers. While the interaction of tillage practices and irrigations has no substantial effect on maximum tillers in this study.

Figure 4: Number of tillers under different treatments. Vertical bars indicate mean ± standard error

Effective and non-effective tillers

Effective and non-effective tillers (m^2) varied from 140.0 ± 1.15 to 358.0 ± 3.46 and 14.00 ± 0.58 to 63.67 ± 2.19 , respectively (Figure 4.3 and 4.4). CT practices compared with MT practices produced 24.28%, 31.31%, 14.15%, and 16.99% higher effective tillers at 0, 2, 4, and 6 irrigations, respectively (Figure 4.3). Moreover, CT practices compared with ZT practices produced 53.57%, 78.70%, 49.37%, and 42.63% higher effective tillers at 0, 2, 4, and 6 irrigations, respectively. ZT practices compared with CT practices produced 13.69%, 13.89%, 31.08%, and 38.89% higher non-effective tillers (m^2) at 0, 2, 4, and 6 irrigations, respectively. Similarly, ZT practices compared with CT practices produced 28.19%, 38.20%, 56.45%, and 78.57%

higher non-effective tillers (m^2) at 0, 2, 4, and 6 irrigations, respectively (Figure 4.4). CT practices compared to MT and ZT practices produced higher effective tillers of 20.59% and 53.86% and lower non-effective tillers of 15.35% and 29.63%, respectively. Six irrigations compared with 0, 2, and 4 irrigations had higher effective tillers (m^2) of 73.30%, 43.87% and 14.23%, respectively. Moreover, six irrigations compared with 0, 2, and 4 irrigations had lower non-effective tillers (m^2) of 66.34%, 46.56%, and 26.61%, respectively. Tillage practices and irrigation had significant effect ($P < 0.001$) on effective and non-effective tillers (m^2). While their interaction effects had substantial effect on effective tillers (m^2) only.

Figure 5 Effective tillers under different treatments. Vertical bars indicate mean ± standard error. Different letters within each treatment indicates significant difference among the treatments ($P < 0.05$). Significance level ^{ns} $P > 0.05$, ^{***} $P < 0.001$

Figure 6: Non-effective tillers under different treatments. Vertical bars indicate mean ± standard error. Different letters within each treatment indicates significant difference among the treatments ($P < 0.05$). Significance level ^{ns} $P > 0.05$, ^{***} $P < 0.001$

Filled and un-filled spikelets

Filled and unfilled spikelet’s per panicle varied from 21 ± 0.58 to 10.67 ± 0.33 and 9.7 ± 0.7 to 4.7 ± 0.3 in all treatments, respectively (Figure 4.5 and 4.6). Compared with MT and ZT practices, CT practices had 10.53%, 7.84%, 3.7%, and 8.62% and 31.25%, 14.58%, 9.80%, and 12.50% substantially higher

filled spikelet’s per panicle at 0, 2, 4, and 6 irrigations, respectively. Number of 6 irrigations had 58.04%, 14.94%, and 9.94% higher filled spikelet’s per panicle compared with 0, 2, and 4 irrigations, respectively. Tillage practices and irrigations substantially ($P < 0.001$) effect the filled spikelet’s per panicle (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Filled spikelet’s per panicle under different treatments. Vertical bars indicate mean ± standard error. Different letters within each treatment indicates significant difference among the treatments ($P < 0.05$).

Significance level ^{ns} $P > 0.05$, ^{*} $P < 0.01$, ^{***} $P < 0.001$

Compared with ZT practices, CT practices had significantly lower unfilled spikelet’s per panicle (Figure 7). While CT and MT practices had no significant higher unfilled spikelet’s per panicle. ZT practices compared with CT practices had 31.82%, 10.53%, 17.65%, and 12.5% lower unfilled spikelet’s per panicle at 0, 2, 4, and 6 irrigations, respectively. Moreover, ZT practices compared with

MT practices had 20.83%, 5.0%, 5.26%, and 28.57% lower unfilled spikelet’s per panicle at 0, 2, 4, and 6 irrigations, respectively. Irrigations substantially effect the unfilled spikelet’s per panicle. Six irrigations had 36%, 20%, and 14.29% lower unfilled spikelet’s per panicle compared with 0, 2, and 4 irrigations, respectively.

Figure 8: Un-filled spikelet’s per panicle under different treatments. Vertical bars indicate mean ± standard error. Different letters within each treatment indicates significant difference among the treatments (P < 0.05).

Significance level ^{ns}P > 0.05, ^{**}P < 0.01, ^{***}P < 0.001

Spike length and grains per spike

Figure 9 illustrated that CT with six irrigation produced maximum spike length (18.3 ± 0.3 cm) and ZT with no irrigation produced minimum spike length (6.0 ± 0.6 cm). CT practices compared with MT practices produced 20.83%, 11.11%, 15.38%, and 14.58% higher spike length at 0, 2, 4, and 6 irrigations, respectively. Similarly, CT practices compared with ZT practices had substantial higher spike length 61.11%, 66.67%, 45.16%, and 52.78%

at 0, 2, 4, and 6 irrigations, respectively. CT compared with MT and ZT had substantially higher 14.97% and 55.05% spike length at all irrigation levels, respectively. Compared with 0, 2, and 4 irrigations, 6 irrigations had 95.77%, 39.0%, and 20.87% higher spike length, respectively. Tillage practices and irrigations had substantial effect on spike length, while tillage practices × irrigations had no significant effect on spike length.

Figure 9: Spike length under different treatments. Vertical bars indicate mean ± standard error. Different letters within each treatment indicates significant difference among the treatments (P < 0.05). Significance level ^{ns}P > 0.05, ^{**}P < 0.01, ^{***}P < 0.001

The maximum number of grains per spike were measured at CT6 (53.0 ± 1.2) and minimum at ZT0 (29.7 ± 0.9) (Figure 10). The grains number per spike was maximum at 6 irrigations followed by 4, 2, and 0 irrigations under all tillage practices. CT practices compared with MT practices increased the grains number per spike 8.57%, 7.44%, 5.07%, and 3.92%, at 0, 2, 4, and 6 irrigations, respectively. Moreover, CT practices compared with ZT practices increased the grains number per spike 28.09%, 28.71%, 23.93%, and 22.31%, at 0, 2, 4, and 6 irrigations,

respectively. Overall, CT practices compared with MT and ZT practices increased 5.66% and 20.26% number of grains per spike, respectively. Six irrigations compared with 0, 2, and 4 irrigations improved the grains per spike 43.51%, 25.57%, and 10.50%, respectively. Tillage practices and irrigations had significant (P < 0.001) effect on grains number per spike. While the interaction of tillage practices and irrigations had no substantial (P > 0.05) effect on number of grains per spike.

Figure 10:Grains per spike under different treatments. Vertical bars indicate mean ± standard error. Different letters within each treatment indicates significant difference among the treatments (P < 0.05). Significance level ^{ns}P > 0.05, ^{**}P < 0.01, ^{***}P < 0.001

Harvesting parameters - 1000 grains weight

The maximum 1000 grains weight were found in CT6 (57.67 ± 1.20 g) and minimum in ZT0 (30.0 ± 1.15 g) (Figure 11). The 1000 grain weight were maximum at 6 irrigations followed by 4, 2, and no irrigation under all tillage practices. CT compared with MT and ZT practices had 16.67%, 12.60%, 11.19%, and 12.34% and 40.0%, 34.91%, 27.20% and 17.69% higher 1000 grains weight at 0, 2, 4, and 6 irrigations, respectively. Overall, at 6 irrigations

compared with 0, 2, and 4 irrigations had 46.30%, 26.06%, and 11.01% significantly higher 1000 grains weight, respectively. CT compared with MT and ZT practices had significantly higher 12.97% and 28.42% 1000 grains weight, respectively. Tillage practices, and irrigations had a substantial (P < 0.05) impact on 1000 grains weight. While tillage practices × irrigations had no substantial (P > 0.05) impact on 1000 grains weight.

Figure 11 1000 grains weight under different treatments. Vertical bars indicate mean ± standard error. Different letters within each treatment indicates significant difference among the treatments (P < 0.05). Significance level ^{ns}P > 0.05, ^{***}P < 0.001

Grain yield

Highest grain yield was measured at CT6 of 5.63 ± 0.02 t ha⁻¹ and minimum at ZT0 of 1.18 ± 0.09 t ha⁻¹ (Figure 12). Under all tillage practices grain yield was obtained maximum at six irrigations and minimum at no irrigation. CT compared with MT practices produced significantly higher 38.63%, 3.85%, 5.12%, and 9.37% grain yield at 0, 2, 4 and 6 irrigations, respectively. While CT compared with ZT practices produced significantly higher grain yield of 57.40%,

15.79%, 19.98%, and 20.63% at 0, 2, 4 and 6 irrigations, respectively. Compared with MT and ZT practices, CT produced substantially higher 8.93% and 12.08% grain yield. Overall, at six irrigations compared with 0, 2, and 4 irrigation produced 205.51%, 84.43%, and 27.76% significantly higher (P < 0.05) grain yield, respectively. Statistical analysis depicted that tillage practices, irrigations, and tillage practices × irrigations substantially (P < 0.001) influenced the grain yield.

Figure 12 Grain yield under different treatments. Vertical bars indicate mean ± standard error. Different letters within each treatment indicates significant difference among the treatments (P < 0.05). Significance level ***P < 0.001

Biomass

Figure 13 presents the biomass measured from the harvested samples. Tillage practices, irrigations, and tillage practices × irrigations substantially (P < 0.001) influenced the biomass. The maximum biomass was measured at CT6 (15.10 ± 0.01 t ha⁻¹) and minimum at ZT0 (4.62 ± 0.09 t ha⁻¹). Biomass was substantially (P < 0.05) higher at 6 irrigations compared with 0, 2, and 4 irrigations under all tillage practices. Compared with MT practices, CT had higher

biomass 20.06%, 16.78%, 10.16% and 4.75% at 0, 2, 4, and 6 irrigations, respectively. Similarly, CT compared with ZT practices had higher biomass 34.97%, 37.09%, 28.49% and 17.85% at 0, 2, 4, and 6 irrigations, respectively. Overall, CT practices compared with MT and ZT practices had 11.10% and 27.58% significantly higher biomass, respectively. Six irrigations had substantially higher biomass of 163.84%, 40.37, and 16.40% compared with 0, 2, and 4 irrigations, respectively.

Figure 13, Biomass (t ha⁻¹) under all treatments. Vertical bars indicate mean ± standard error. Different letters within each treatment indicates significant difference among the treatments (P < 0.05). Significance level ***P < 0.001

Water productivity

Water productivity (WP) is the relationship between the economic output and the amount of water used for production. As the water supply increases, WP decreases, leading to a reduction in overall water productivity. Maximum WP was estimated 1.90 ± 0.01 kg m⁻³ under CT2 treatment and a minimum 0.85 ± 0.00 kg m⁻³ under ZT6 treatment (Figure 14). Statistical analysis showed that tillage practices, irrigations, and interaction of tillage practices and irrigations showed a prominent (P < 0.001) effect on WP. Compared with MT practices, CT had substantially (P < 0.05) higher WP of 38.63, 3.85%,

5.12%, and 9.37% at 0, 2, 4, and 6 irrigations, respectively. Similarly, CT compared with ZT practices had substantially higher (P < 0.05) WP of 57.40%, 15.79%, 19.98%, and 20.63% at 0, 2, 4, and 6 irrigations, respectively. Compared with MT and ZT, CT practices increased substantially WP 13.84% and 27.95%, respectively. Overall, at 2 irrigations compared with 4 and 6 irrigations improved WP 47.02% and 90.77%, respectively. ZT recorded lower WP than CT and MT in this study. A decrease in WP was observed as the number of irrigations increased. The highest WP was achieved with two irrigations.

Figure 14: Water productivity (kg m⁻³) in all treatments. Vertical bars indicate mean ± standard error. Different letters within each treatment indicates significant difference among the treatments (P < 0.05). Significance level **P < 0.01, ***P < 0.001

DISCUSSION

Tillage is a key element which plays an essential role in crop development, nutrients, and water availability to the crop. Arif et al. (2007) concluded that tillage practices caused soil disturbance and loss of soil organic matter content. This can be overcome by adopting MT or ZT having lower soil disturbance compared with CT practices. Halvorson et al. (2001) also reported that tillage practice influenced the soil physical properties, crop yield, and nitrogen uptake. Benbi et al. (1991) observed that tillage practices changed the soil properties, soil environment, and ultimately impacted crop root growth and distribution and yield as well. In this chapter deals with the discussion on the results of the effects of CT, MT, and ZT practices with 0, 2, 4, and 6 irrigations on crop growth and grain yield of wheat crop.

Effect of different tillage practices and irrigation on growth parameters

Plant height is an essential trait in wheat because it affects plant structure and ultimately grain yield (Bellucci et al., 2015; Hassan et al., 2019). Plant height peaked at the flowering stage under both tillage practices. At 6 irrigations plants grew faster compared with 4, 2, and 0 irrigation under all tillage

practices. CT compared with MT and ZT practice has overall higher plant height at all irrigation levels. Similar results were measured by Yildirim et al. (2018) that plant height was significantly higher under CT over RT practice over two years of study in wheat crop. It was seen those higher irrigation treatments (6) produced substantially higher plant height than the low irrigation scheduling treatments (0, 2, and 4) under all tillage practices. In general, CT at 6 irrigations produced substantially higher crop height compared with MT and ZT practices (Figure 4.1).

The maximum plant height observed under CT6 of 74.0 ± 0.58 cm. Whereas, minimum plant height was measured under ZT0 treatment of 42.67 ± 0.88 cm. The study highlights the significant impact of different treatments on wheat crop height throughout the cropping season. These findings are close to the reports of Alam et al. (2022) who found that the maximum plant height of wheat crop was observed 79 cm. Moreover, Jakhar et al. (2005) and Idnani et al. (2012) observed the same results.

The highest tiller was measured under CT6 treatment (403.67 ± 4.26) and the lowest under ZT0 treatment (312 ± 4.73). Tillers per square meter have a significant impact on wheat yield. For wheat producers, it is crucial to monitor and maximize the

tillers since it can have a substantial impact on the wheat crop's final production. Tillers increased rapidly under CT compared with MT and ZT practices at the respective irrigation levels. As the irrigation level raised number of tillers also raised under all tillage practices. It was measured that CT compared with MT and ZT practices at 0, 2, 4, and 6 irrigations produced a greater number of tillers. The maximum number of tillers was measured under CT practice at 6 irrigations and least under ZT practice (Figure 4.2). Results illustrated that by increasing irrigation tillers also improved. Similarly, McDonald et al. (1984) observed measured highest number of tillers in higher irrigation events. Irrigating with 2 irrigations under all tillage practices drastically lowered the tillers. This may be linked with the crop water stress reduced the vegetative growth. Under CT practice irrigating at 6 irrigations produced more tillers. Statistically analysis indicates that tillage practices and irrigation effects significantly on maximum number of tillers while the interaction of tillage practices and irrigation scheduling has no significant on maximum number of tillers. These results are confirmed with the study of Kanwal et al. (2020). The tillers were not considerably affected by irrigation regimes. These results are supported by Khan et al. (2009) that no irrigation substantially decreases the tillers. Under all tillage practices tillers numbers followed the trend of $0 > 2 > 4 > 6$ irrigations. The assessment of yield under the existing conditions is influenced by the tillers. When it comes to producing yields through the creation of tillers, wheat is among the most important cereals (Figure 4.2).

Effect of different tillage practices on crop harvest parameters

The quantity of tillers considered to be effective depends on the amount of grain a crop produces. In other words, productive tillers are those that result in fertile spikes that increase the crop's overall output. Tillers that don't help a crop produce grain are said to be non-effective tillers. Evaluating the proportion of non-effective tillers can reveal information about the crop's growth and yield. An abundance of non-effective tillers may be a sign that the crop is stressed or experiencing other issues that might reduce its potential yield. Crop production and output can be

increased by determining and resolving the root causes of non-effective tillers. These findings are agreed with Alam et al. (2022) and Mukherjee et al. (2022) both studies observed that the maximum effective tillers varied from 165 to 246. The results of non-effective tillers agreed with the study of Gupta et al. (2021) found that the non-effective tillers were between 67 to 72 under different treatments (Figure 4.3 and 4.4).

Under all tillage treatments, non-effective tillers were measured least at no irrigation followed by 2 and 4 irrigations. Which illustrated that effective tillers numbers improved with a number of irrigations (Ali et al., 2007). At all tillage practices, lower effective tiller numbers and higher non-effective tiller numbers at no irrigation and 2 irrigations were results due to prolong irrigation gap, causing water stress on the plant.

At all tillage practices at no irrigation yielded the lowest filled spikes and higher un-filled spikes number. Identical results were measured by Bhunia et al. (2015) that the yield traits i.e., effective tillers, spike length, grains per panicle, and 1000 grains weight improved with higher soil moisture content for irrigation. Therefore, higher-filled panicles and lower un-filled panicle in the order of $0 > 2 > 4 > 6$ irrigations under all tillage practices. It showed that at all tillage practices combined with six irrigations may provide favorable soil environment to ameliorate yield attributes. Filled spikelet's have not reduced substantially at 2 and 4 irrigations under all tillage practices but decreased significantly at no irrigation due to water stress appearing at flowering and maturity stage. At milking stage water stress caused plants to be vulnerable to attack of diseases poor grain filling, therefore higher number of unfilled spikelet's at no irrigation under all tillage practices (Figure 4.5 and 4.6).

Results indicated that the number of irrigations and the selection of suitable tillage practices can significantly affect the formation and progress of wheat crops. The spike length greatly increased with increasing the number of irrigations, which is consistent with the findings given by Kanwal et al. (2020), measured a tendency in favor of irrigation for wheat yield, the spike length is a crucial element. More grain is produced per spike because of larger spikes, increasing wheat yield. Under CT practice

length of spike varied from 9.67 ± 0.88 to 18.33 ± 0.33 cm, MT from 8.0 ± 0.88 to 1.15 ± 0.58 cm, and ZT from 6.0 ± 0.58 to 12.00 ± 0.58 cm. CT compared with MT and ZT had substantially higher 14.97% and 55.05% spike length at all irrigation levels, respectively (Figure 4.7 and 4.8). Identical results were obtained by Leghari et al. (2015) that maximum spike length and number of grains under CT practice followed by MT and ZT practices in two years (2008 and 2009) of study. CT compared with MT and ZT had substantially higher 14.97% and 55.05% spike length at all irrigation levels, respectively. Overall, CT practices compared with MT and ZT practices increased 5.66% and 20.26% number of grains per spike, respectively. Our results are agreed well with Gholami et al. (2014) that CT compared to RT and ZT practices had 2.55% and 31.86% higher spike length in wheat crop, respectively. Moreover, CT compared to RT and ZT practices had 19.15% and 25.68% higher grains per spike, respectively.

The 1000 grains weight varied from 30 ± 1.15 to 57.67 ± 1.20 g (Figure 4.9). The 1000-grains weight of wheat is an essential yield parameter and fairly contribute to wheat grain productivity. Therefore, it is found that there were higher differences in 1000 grains weight under different tillage practices and irrigations. These results are in line with Kanwal et al. (2020) measured the 1000 grains weight range from 40 to 42 g under different irrigation treatments. Higher 1000 grains weight under six irrigations might be due to higher translocation of photosynthates towards grain due to enough soil water content in root zone. On the other hand, at no irrigation produced lower 1000 grains weight due to lower availability of nutrients from soil solution. Wajid et al. (2002) reported substantial effect of irrigation on 1000 grains weight. Our results are in line with Gezahegn et al. (2019) that CT compared to RT (residue removed) produced 2% higher 1000 grains weight of durum wheat. The highest amount of soil moisture has been observed in CT systems under different arid climates (Meidani et al., 2012; Mohammadi et al., 2009). As a result, any tillage practice capable of retaining soil moisture content during critical growth stage i.e., grain filling will eventually enhance productivity as it limits grain hollowness and increases 1000 grains weight.

The CT practice was found to be superior compared to MT and ZT practices; irrigating with six irrigations has yielded the maximum grain yield. Under all tillage practices six irrigations produced substantially higher grain yield compared with 2 and 4 irrigations. This might be associated with prolong irrigation gap results water stress. Identical conclusions were drawn by Jha et al. (2019), English (1990), El-Hendawy et al. (2007), and Kang et al. (2002) that different irrigation regimes substantially influenced the grain yield. Our results agreed well with Gezahegn et al. (2019) that CT compared with RT with residue removed and ZT treatment had 19.44% and 116.61%, respectively higher grain yield compared to CT treatment for growing Tef at Alem Tena site in central Ethiopia. Compared with MT and ZT practices, CT produced substantially higher 8.93% and 12.08% grain yield.

Grain yield was higher under CT compared with MT and ZT practices and six irrigations had substantially higher grain yield compared with 0, 2, and 4 irrigations, respectively. Grain yield under CT at 6 irrigations increased 202.65%, 18.82%, and 7.57% compared to 0, 2, and 4 irrigations, respectively. Similarly, grain yield under MT at 6 irrigations increased 283.63%, 3.69%, and 3.38%, compared to 0, 2, and 4 irrigations, respectively (Figure 4.10). Moreover, ZT with 6 irrigations increased grain yield 294.92%, 14.05%, and 6.99%, compared with 0, 2, and 4 irrigations, respectively. Pikul et al. (1999) and Pikul et al. (2003) observed that sub-soiling (CT) or deep tillage decreased soil compaction and enhanced grain yield. Bennie and Botha, (1986) observed that deep tillage (CT) might loose sub-soil compacted layers and enhance root growth and penetration, thus improve crop yield. Moreover, CT keeps wheat ripening adequately but MT and RT practices delayed crop maturity which yields lower grain yield. Our results agreed well with Chauhdary et al. (2016), who found a rise of 13% in yield under CT as compared to MT and ZT treatments. The findings of Bakhsh et al. (2018) and Iqbal et al. (2022) were similar. Our results are agreed well with Gholami et al. (2014) that CT compared to MT and ZT has 25.05% and 30.73% higher grain yield, respectively. The choice of tillage methods had a noteworthy influence on grain yield, with wheat planted under CT yielding more compared to MT and ZT

approaches. This difference in yield was attributed to superior growth and yield characteristics. It is suggested that the reasonable yield achieved with MT methods could be attributed to advantageous factors such as better moisture availability, which likely assisted the crop in competing with those planted using conventional tillage practices (Gupta et al., 2007; Jain et al., 2007; Kumar et al., 2005). It's well-established that the growth, development, and ultimately, the yield of crops is significantly affected by the presence of soil moisture (Alem, 1993).

Increasing the frequency of irrigation resulted in higher grain yields, with the maximum yield observed at six irrigations. This increase was primarily attributed to improvements in yield attributes. Studies by Singh (2004), Thakuria et al. (2004), and Yadav et al. (2009) also noted that more frequent irrigation led to better soil moisture availability, facilitating enhanced nutrient uptake by the crops and improved assimilation of photosynthates into the crop sink. Conversely, due to lower effective tillers, spikelet fill per spike, reduced spike length, fewer grains per spike, smaller 1000 grains weight, lower grain yields were recorded with 0 and 2 irrigations. The crop under the MT responded positively to irrigation. In the case of the ZT crop, the grain yield increase was higher with increasing irrigation levels, peaking at 6 irrigations. However, with less frequent irrigation (2 irrigations) in the ZT system, lower yield-related factors, grain yield, and biomass were observed, possibly due to soil compaction.

Six irrigations had substantially higher 163.84%, 40.37%, and 16.40% biomass compared with 0, 2, and 4 irrigations, respectively (Figure 4.11). Overall, CT practices compared with MT and ZT practices had 11.10% and 27.58% significantly higher biomass, respectively. The biomass rose linearly with the irrigation amount. Lower biomass at no irrigation and 2 irrigations under all tillage practices linked with the overall lower vegetative growth. Therefore, lower irrigation numbers caused the plant under water stress and ultimately decreased biomass compared to higher irrigations (Kang et al., 2002).

Effect of different tillage practices on water productivity

Water productivity (WP) is the relationship between economic output and water use for production. As the water supply increases, WP decreases, reducing overall productivity. The water productivity observed between 1.90 ± 0.01 to 0.85 ± 0.00 kg m⁻³. Tillage practices, irrigations, and the interaction of tillage practices significantly affect WP. CT practices had higher WP than MT practices, and overall WP improved at 2 irrigations. ZT recorded lower WP than CT and MT. The decline in water productivity at higher irrigation levels may be ascribed to water loss. Interestingly, the escalation in yield with increased irrigation did not correspond proportionally to the rise in evapotranspiration (ET) at elevated irrigation levels, leading to a reduction in water productivity (WP) at higher irrigation intensities. This observation aligns with the findings of Pradhan et al. (2014). This correlation is consistent with the results reported by Bandyopadhyay et al. (2021), indicated that $(RP = 0.2486WP + 1.4315)$ for every unit increase in water productivity, the relative yield increased by 0.25 times.

CONCLUSIONS

In Pakistan, there is a severe shortage of irrigation water during the Rabi season. Therefore, water conservation and efficient use are critical in agricultural research. This study investigated the effects of CT, MT, and ZT practices and 0, 2, 4, and 6 irrigation events on the crop growth, yield, and biomass of wheat crops. Compared to MT and ZT practices, CT significantly improved crop growth, yield attributes, grain yield, and WP of wheat crop. Moreover, 6 irrigation events of 75 mm compared with 0, 2, and 4 irrigations substantially improved the crop growth, yield, and biomass of wheat crop. This study revealed that CT over MT and ZT practice has substantially improved wheat yields (8.93% and 12.08%), biomass (11.10% and 27.58%), and crop WP (13.84% and 27.95%). Overall, 2 irrigations improved the WP 47.02% and 90.77% compared with 4 and 6 irrigations, respectively. Irrigation with 6 numbers may be adopted to improve the crop growth, yield, and WP of wheat crop compared with 0, 2, and 4 irrigations. CT with 6 irrigations will be

the optimum approach for wheat cultivation for the silty clay loam soil of Shaheed Benazirabad.

Recommendations

In this study, CT compared with MT and ZT practices with six irrigations improved crop growth, grain yield, and biomass of wheat crop. Therefore, CT practice with six irrigations is recommended for higher yield for climatic conditions in Shaheed Benazirabad and other regions sharing the same climatic conditions. Moreover, it is recommended to further study different tillage practices under different regions and years, as well as economic analysis. This study provides practical implications for farmers, agronomists, and policymakers.

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